

Postmodernism and Salman Rushdie

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Abstract

Salman Rushdie has established himself as one of the most powerful modern writers. With his famous novels *Grimus* (1975), *Midnight's Children* (1981), *Shame* (1983) and *Satanic Verses* (1988), he has emerged as a novelist of repute. The theme in his novels is fairly varied. Rushdie is a trend setter. He has conjured up a new trend by mixing free-flight-fairy tale with savage political indictment. The concept of postmodernism includes a wide variety of subjects, including art, architecture, music, film, literature, sociology, communication, fashion and technology. In postmodern art we note self-reflexivity and consciousness, fragmentation and discontinuity, ambiguity and emphasis on the destructured, decentered, dehumanized subject. Nowadays there are some sub-continental writers giving voice to the broad political, religious, historical and cultural experiences of South Asia. These writers are very much interested in India and write in English. Salman Rushdie is the first and the most prominent sub-continental writer, writing in English who constructs Indian history and Indian experience within the context of this hybridity. His novels have personal touches and the element of subjectivity is found in his novels.

Keywords :- Postmodernism, Culture, History, Fragmentation

Postmodern literature is a form of literature marked by reliance on narrative techniques such as fragmentation, unreliable narrator, parody, dark humour and paradox. Postmodernism came into prominence after the second World War and it is often seen as response or reaction against modernism. As a result postmodern authors often highlight the possibility of multiple meanings within a single literary work or a complete lack of meaning. In literature we note certain features regarding postmodernism, for example, literature tends to be non-traditional. We experiment techniques in literature. Parody and pastiche are a few examples of the features of postmodernism.

J.A. Cuddon defines postmodernism as, "A general (and sometimes controversial) term used to refer to the changes, developments and tendencies which have taken place (and are taking place) in literature, art, music, architecture, philosophy, etc. since 1940s or 1950s."¹ It begins when modernism is over. Postmodernism is a complicated set of ideas. It took a clear shape around the mid-1980s.

Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* is representative of what has been called postmodern fiction. We find elements of fantasy, history and mythology which create a nuanced presentation of the narrative. The novel portrays a fictionalised history of India from 1915 to the Emergency of 1976. Rushdie believes that one can not separate history and the individual. Both find access into each other and the writer examines one in the context of the other. Niel Ten Kortenaar comments, "Salman Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* is commonly as a national allegory giving imaginative form to India and its history."²

Rushdie's fiction depicts the

complex postmodern world in a postmodern style. All what he writes symbolizes his vision about history and its impact on the reality of his Indian society and life. Also, Rushdie, like most of postmodern writers, endeavours to liberate himself from the traditional conventions to create a world that is far away from reality that has no borders. Rushdie presents innovative narrative techniques that are quite different from the contemporary writers and that makes a complicated and very difficult work of fiction in *Midnight's*

Children. He uses magical realism, metafiction and intertextuality in order to break the tradition of the Indian English novels. He has presented the history mixed with the fiction. About history he writes in 'Shame' "History is a natural selection. Mutant versions the past struggle for dominance; new species of fact arise, and old, saurian truths go to the wall, blindfolded and smoking last cigarettes. Only the mutations of the strong survive. The weak, the anonymous, the defeated leave few marks; field patterns, axe-heads, folk-tales, broken pitchers, burial mounds, the fading memory of their youthful beauty. History loves only those who dominate her; it is the relationship of mutual enslavement."³

The novel *Midnight's Children* is full of subjective element. The events in the life of Saleem Sinai are like the events in the life of Salman Rushdie to an extent. Like the protagonist he was born in Bombay. In the book his grandparents are Kashmiri. In real life his parents were Kashmiri originally. When we go through the novel we can find many events that match with the life of the writer himself. The novel is highly autobiographical.

In *Midnight's Children* there is the intermingling and intermixing of different cultures.

The story begins in Kashmir and we find much of the life and culture of Kashmir. When the writer, in the book, moves to Bombay he puts before us the life of Bombay. He presents the glimpses of the people of different religions who have different life styles. He also presents secularism in the novel through Dr. Aziz who has secular ideas. In the novel quarrels among the people of different religions are also presented. He has presented the critical issues of nationalism and partition. Events of pre-independence and post-independence like Quit-India movement, Jallianwala Bagh incident, partition of country, emergency, political impropriety, religious riots etc. are presented in the book. In the novel he puts virtually all the 20th century history of India. We get a sharp picture of emergency in the book:

"While all over India policemen were arresting all opposition leaders except members of the pro-Moscow communists and also school teachers lawyers poets newspapermen trade-unionists, in fact anyone who had ever made the mistake of sneezing during the Madam's speeches and when the three contortionists had washed the baby and wrapped it in an old sari and brought it out for its father to see, at exactly the same moments, the word Emergency was being heard for the first time, and suspension-of-civil rights and censorship-of-the-press and armoured-units-on-special-alert and arrest of sub-versive elements,"⁴

Salman Rushdie's another novel 'Shame' exhibits the best features of a postmodern novel by a style of magic realism by touching some political issues and some significant characters in a turbulent Pakistan in the way of historiographic fiction. In that novel we meet a discursive and fragmentary narration. The most remarkable feature of postmodern fiction in 'Shame' is that the narrator addresses to the audience directly and makes comments, explanations and criticism on the events. The writer shows that there were expectation in the hearts of people about post-independence country. But these expectations were thrown into the air by the repression of politics. Here we find some events that were responsible for the civil strife in Pakistan. The theme is woven around the superstitions and backward aspects of Islamic society. Shame and shamelessness go together. We note the social and religious repression of women regarding dress code, sexual freedom etc. and these are highly criticised by the writer.

The narrator in 'Shame' also plays the notion of time in the novel by turning back and faith in time by some flashbacks and different time images. There is a circle where all kind of times, subjects and events are put on the agenda frequently and one after the other, which suggests the postmodern structure in 'Shame.'

'Shame' deserves being called as a postmodern novel in the light of the key

characteristics of postmodern fiction such as narrative fragmentation and reflexivity, the decentring of the subject, fictional framing of devices and the displacement of the real by simulacra, magic realism and historiographic metafiction.

Salman Rushdie's another novel 'The Moor's Last Sigh' has a fairly wide canvas focusing of the political, the national experience and a national consciousness. Rushdie brings out the religious ruling that marked the history of India. In this novel the writer gives an elaborate picture of a family's encounter with Indian history. De Gama Zogoiby and Aurora Zogoiby are the characters who symbolize the victims of modern India and their story is the story of their encounter with major and minor events of modern India.

National and political issues and events we also get in this novel. The writer tells that Cochin, Travancore, Mysore and Hyderabad were technically not a part of British India. They had their own princes. When Amritsar massacre took place Tagore returned his Knighthood. "When the Russian Revolution Shook the world, when the great war ended, when the news of the Amritsar massacre filtered down from the north and destroyed the Anglophilia of almost every Indian (the nobel laureate Rabindranath Tagore, returned his Knighthood to the king.)"⁵ The writer presents the expectations of a new country which will be secular having all goods. Nehru's demand for independence was a pre-condition for India's support in the war efforts. Jinnah's demand for a separate nation for Muslims is also there in the book. In the beginning of the novel life in Kerala is presented and in the other half of the novel life in Bombay is presented. Religious aspects and racism are also presented. Therefore we get the mixed life of India in this book.

Rushdie uses postmodern elements as a style of discourse in the novel. The actions and happenings in course of plot is beautifully painted in a canvas of postmodernism. It could also be read for understanding what postmodernism is and how it could be adopted in a literary work of art. By twists of language and characters Rushdie provides a postmodern lesson through the novel.

References

1. J.A. Cuddon, A Dictionary of Literary Terms, (New Delhi : Andrew Oustsea, 1971), P.689.
2. Niel Ten Kortenaar, "Midnight's Children and The Allegory of History," ARIEL, 1995, P.41.
3. Salman Rushdie, Shame (London : Jonathan Cape Ltd., 1983) P. 124.
4. Salman Rushdie, Midnight's Children (London : Vintage, 1995) P. 419.
5. Salman Rushdie, The Moor's Last Sigh (London : Vintage, 1996), P. 22.